

DEVELOPMENT OF SCHEMATIC DIAGRAM OF SYSTEM AUTOMATION

Ismanov Muhammadziyo

PhD of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology

e-mail: ismanovm91@gmail.com

Toshpo'latov Ibroxim

Magistr of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology

Annotation: The goal of building automation is to provide efficient and high-quality service to all equipment. Automation is a field of science and technology that considers the theory of automatic control, automatic production systems and the construction of the technical construction that constitutes them.

Key words: *Chemical, atmospheric, boiler room, Compressor, Project, system, electrical, SCADA, Scheme, panels, consoles, cabinets, electrical networks, Transport.*

Introduction

To read a diagram means to obtain from it the information necessary to perform a particular task in the course of design, installation, commissioning, operation or training. For example, reading structural and functional automation diagrams, they get an idea of the structure of the device, functional units, connections between them and their interaction. Reading schematic diagrams, the principle of operation of the automation system, as a whole or its individual block, the operation capabilities of its device, the interaction of individual elements of the circuit, its operating modes, settings (current, time) and other parameters of devices and devices.

Reading diagrams or tables of external connections devices and automation equipment, including panels, consoles, cabinets, reception and selection devices

(sensors), methods of laying electrical and pipeline lines, external connections between network wires using boxes, switches, modules gives information about, boxes, etc.

Reading the connection diagrams or tables of connections and connections of shields, consoles and cabinets, as well as closely related drawings of overviews of these structures, determines the arrangement of devices, installation products, their marking, material, vein and direction of communication. lines within a single structure.

When reading diagrams of automation functions, it is recommended to follow the following sequence:

2) study the technological process and the interaction of all devices, blocks and devices involved in it, start familiarization with the automation project and explanatory notes to the technological part;

3) determines the organization of control and management points of this technological process;

4) establish a list of nodes for monitoring, signaling and automatic regulation and control of electric drives provided for in this scheme.

In this case, control devices are displayed near the technological equipment and sensors, and the control rings are indicated with the corresponding Arabic numerals. Actuators and sensors do not have alphanumeric characters. The automation scheme obtained as a result of the development provides information about the automated technological object and allows you to familiarize yourself with and study the schematic diagrams of individual functional units and devices.

Figure 1. electrical scheme.

Under pressure, the refrigerant enters the evaporator through the throttle valve, where evaporation occurs due to a sharp drop in pressure. In this case, the cooler takes heat from the inner walls of the evaporator, and the evaporator removes heat from the circuit of the ground, as a result of which it appears constant cooling. The compressor takes the refrigerant from the evaporator, compresses it, as a result of which the temperature of the refrigerant rises and pushes it into the condenser. In addition, the refrigerant, which is heated as a result of compression in the condenser, releases the received heat (temperature at the level of 85-125 °C). heating cycle and finally it turns into a liquid state. The process repeats until the required temperature is reached, the thermostat opens the electrical circuit, and the compressor stops. When the temperature drops in the heating circuit, the thermostat turns the compressor back on. In heat pumps, the refrigerant performs a reverse Carnot cycle.

Functional diagram of the control automation system, temperature of the heat pump

In the combustion chamber, fuel is burned by converting chemical energy

into heat energy. About half of the fuel heat is absorbed by the heating surface located in the combustion chamber, where the combustion products are cooled to a temperature of 900-1100 °C (depending on the type of fuel being burned). Then the combustion products enter the horizontal gas channel, and then the vertical. The boiler unit is serviced by auxiliary mechanisms and devices. These include: gas control station, exhaust and draft fans, network pumps. Blowers are used to provide the air needed during the combustion process. Smoke fans are designed to remove waste gases from the boiler room. Flue gases are released into the atmosphere through chimneys and then through chimneys. A network pump is installed to create circulation in the heating system and boiler. Chemically treated water is used to feed the heat network. natural water contains mechanical and colloidal impurities, dissolved salts and gases. Therefore, the water intended for makeup is supplied by the raw water pump to the raw water heater, where it is heated to a temperature of 18-20 ° C. Then the heated water enters mechanical filters, where it is cleaned of mechanical impurities and sodium-cation exchange filters, where hardness salts are removed. After chemical water treatment, the clarified, softened water enters the degassed water cooler, the chemically treated water heater, where it is heated to a temperature of 70-75 °C. After the heat exchanger, the water enters a vacuum deaerator to remove oxygen and carbon dioxide. Through the deaerated water cooler, degassed water enters the degassed water tank, from where it is supplied to the make-up pump of the hot water boiler network pump for suction. The proposed system is a control and measurement system, designed for:

automation of steam parameter control in units of the water heating boiler house of OAO Perm pig farm Maisky village;

Automating control of the enterprise's heat supply parameters;

Automating control of hot water supply parameters of the enterprise;

Automation of control of technical parameters of water;

Figure 2. Functional diagram.

Functional diagram symbol: TE is the primary measuring conductor for the measurement

local set temperature;

1 - compressor;

2 - low level heat source (LHL);

3 – heat pump evaporator;

4 - heat pump condenser;

5 - high-level heat consumer (HTP);

6 - low temperature heat exchanger;

7 - coolant flow regulator;

8 – high temperature heat exchanger;

AI is an input module on a microcontroller for analog signals;

AO - output module on the microcontroller for analog signals;

DI is an input module on a microcontroller for discrete signals;

DO is an output module on a microcontroller for discrete signals.

Software development Visualization of the project in the SCADA

system

They may be involved in developing software for computer games, business applications, or medical devices. Those in this career path are adept at working with systems theory and understanding the technical limitations of the hardware they are developing software to control. Teams of experts work together on larger efforts, and software developers usually work closely with computer programmers. In some cases, developers write the code themselves instead of giving instructions to programmers.

Figure 3. User interface.

The computer controlling the system will be in the control room with a fixed number 3.4 process hot and cold supply. The programmed controller regulates the work of the heat pump, control sensors are installed on the heat pump that show the temperature and pressure of the heat pump. The room temperature is set by the user.

Figure 4. Module 1 - Digital I/O outputs.

Figure 5. Module 2 - Discrete

Conclusion

Controllers from different manufacturers were also considered and the most suitable Siemens SIMATIC S7 controller was selected based on certain factors. In the chapter "Development of technical support" a basic, functional diagram of automation is developed. In the "Software development" section, the software structure, electrical diagram, visualization of the heat pump climate control system were developed and the program code was compiled. A business case for system development is presented and development costs are calculated.

REFERENCES

1. Ismonovich K. A., Abdusamatugli I. M. Modeling the Method of Linear Approximation of Signals in SPLC (Sensor Programmable Logic Controller) //International Journal on Orange Technologies. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 10. – C. 55-59.
2. Ismonovich K. A., Muhammadziyo I. Mathematical Modeling of Heat Flux Distribution in Raw Cotton Stored in Bunt //Engineering. – 2020. – T. 12. – №. 8. – C. 591-599.
3. Mardonov B., Tadaeva Y., Muhammadziyo I. Experimental and theoretical studies of vibrational motion of raw cotton on inclined mesh surface //International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research. – 2014. – T. 9. – C. 78-85.
4. Muhammadziyo I. Research Of Characteristics And Analysis Of Calculations Of Optoelectronic Hydrometers Of Automatic Control //Solid State Technology. – 2020. – T. 63. – №. 6. – C. 14910-14916.